

A Theoretical Understanding of Financial Inclusion in India

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ABSTRACT

Even after more than 65 years of Independence, a majority of the country's population still do not have a bank account. As a result, this caused financial instability and pauperism among the lower income group who do not have access to financial products and services. In order to achieve inclusive development and growth, the expansion of financial services to all sections of society is the sine qua non of any open and efficient society and Financial Inclusion is one such step in this direction. Financial Inclusion is a relatively new socio-economic concept in India that aims to provide delivery of financial services at affordable costs to vast sections of disadvantaged and low income groups. Availability of banking and payment services to the entire population without discrimination is the prime objective of the idea.

The present paper shows how financial inclusion and financial literacy have been important policies for quite some time, and how government and Reserve Bank of India have been pushing the concept and idea of financial inclusion, as it is a critical step that requires political will, bureaucratic support and dogged persuasion. The paper also presents an assimilation of data for select public sector banks. The authors have made an attempt to analyse the data critically.

INTRODUCTION

It has been found that financial services are used only by a section of the population. There is a demand for these financial services but it has not been provided or if provided has not been able to achieve their objectives. Unfortunately the excluded regions and also those living in harsh climate conditions where it becomes difficult to provide these formal channels of financial services and as a result they have to rely on informal channels for availing finance which is usually at exorbitant rates and it is a global phenomena. In 2012, approximately 2.5 billion adults, just over, do not use formal financial services to save or borrow. 2.2 billion of these unsaved adults live in Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Middle East.

When we talk about financial inclusion from the perspective of India, the position is even worst. India despite having higher economic growth rates than most developed countries in recent years, a majority of country's population still remains unbanked. As per 2012 data, it is estimated that about 40% of Indians lack access even to the simplest kind of formal financial services. Only 55% of population had deposit accounts and 9% had credit accounts with the banks. Just 18% had debit cards and less than 2%

had credit cards. In order to achieve inclusive development and growth the expansion of financial services to all sections of society is important.

The solution lies in including or making available the financial services to the excluded sections of population, very often they being belonging to poor and underprivileged sections or now known as concept of Financial Inclusion.

As defined by the RBI 'Financial Inclusion is the process of ensuring access to appropriate financials products and services needed by vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low income groups at an affordable cost in a fair and transparent manner by mainstream institutional players.

Thus Financial Inclusion is the delivery of financial services at affordable costs to vast sections of disadvantaged and low income groups.

Banking

- SAVING AND PAYMENT THROUGH ATM

CREDIT

- LOW INTEREST RATE

INVESTMENT

- MUTUAL FUNDS ,PENSION PLANS ETC

INSURANCE

- LIFE INSURANCE AND GENERAL INSURANCE

In the Indian context the term "Financial Inclusion" was used for the first time in April 2005 in the annual policy statement presented by Y. Venugopal Reddy, Governor, Reserve Bank of India. It is a relatively new socio-economic concept that aims to change this dynamic by providing financial services at affordable costs to the underprivileged, who might not otherwise be aware of or able to afford these services.

Analysing Financial Inclusion from India's perspective, there is both good and bad news. Good news is that between 2011 and 2014, India has fared well with regards to number of account holders. In 2014, 53% adults are reported to have bank accounts, which is sharp increase from 35% in 2011. Also banking penetration has drastically increased in rural areas between 2011 and 2014 from 33% to 50% respectively.

However, as promising these numbers look, unfortunately financial inclusion goal in India is far from achieved. As per report of World Bank's Development Research Group 'Global Financial Inclusion Database (Global Findex)':

- **The poor are still excluded:** 56% of those adults (% age 15+) who come under 'poorest 40%' are still unbanked, compared to 41% of those who belong to 'richest 60%'.
- **Access does not mean usage:** Many Indians have access to bank accounts but they are not using them. 43% of account holders did not make any deposits or withdrawals in their bank accounts in the past year; yet only 14% saved with formal saving accounts. 46% of adults (% age 15+) borrowed in the previous year; but only 6% did so from formal institutions.
- **The power of the informal financial sources:** There has been increasing use of informal financial services for financial needs, particularly when it comes to borrowing. 13% adults (% age 15+) from friends and relatives.
- **Gender disparity in financial inclusion:** more women have bank accounts today; however, the gender gap has not narrowed. There was an 18 point difference in 2011 (44% male and 26% female with bank accounts) and there is a 19 point difference in 2014 (62% male and 43% female with bank accounts).
- **Cash is still the king:** Even after prevalence of credit/ debit cards, mobile phones, ATMs, shop-based terminals, banking agents etc, cash still predominates the mode of transaction. 20% of adults (% age 15+) reported to have debit cards in the previous year. All types of bills or fees were paid in cash; for example, 99% of these adults paid in cash (6% reported of using a bank account as well).
- **Mobile banking still a NO:** In India the interbank Mobile Payment system (IMPS) has been launched; yet only 2% adults have mobile accounts (58% of adults in Kenya have mobile accounts).

Therefore it is important to realize that account ownership is a first step towards financial inclusion. But what really matters is whether people are actually using their accounts.

Why Financial Inclusion?

The importance of financial inclusion in India has been primarily because of these reasons:

1. Providing a platform for inculcating the habit to save: The position of such disadvantaged and low income groups has been vulnerable due to absence of savings. Presence of banking services and products aims to provide a critical tool to inculcate the habit to save, as people move away from traditional modes of parking their savings in lands, buildings, bullions etc.
2. Creating Formal Credit Avenues: The problem with the unbanked population has been its dependency on informal channels of credit such as family, friends and money lenders. Thus availability of formal banking channels shall promote the entrepreneurial spirit of the masses to increase outputs and prosperity in the countryside.
3. Plug gaps and leaks in public subsidies and welfare programmes: Very often a considerable sum of money which is meant for poorest of poor does not actually reach them, as most of it believed to leak in large system of government bureaucracy, as a result unable to reach the intended parties. To avoid this government is therefore, pushing for direct cash transfers to beneficiaries through their bank accounts rather than subsidizing products and making cash payments.

BACKGROUND

Initiatives taken by Reserve bank of India for financial inclusion

- NO FRILL ACCOUNT
- OVERDRAFT IN SAVING BANK ACCOUNT
- SIMPLIFICATION OF SAVING BANK ACCOUNT OPENING FORM
- FLEXIBLE APPROACH FOR KYC
- MULTILINGUAL WEBSITES
- KISAN CREDIT CARD
- GENERAL CREDIT CARD
- BUSINESS CORRESPONDENCE AND FACILITATORS
- RURAL INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT
- SELF HELP GROUP BANK LINKAGE PROGRAMME
- OPENING OF BANKS IN UNBANKED VILLAGES

2005

On 11 November Facility of no frill accounts was introduced by Reserve Bank of India which means that banks will open zero balance or minimum balance account for financially excluded people. In the same year banks were also encouraged to provide banking services and micro finance to all segment of population. All commercial banks were also advised to publicise the policy in order to attract maximum underprivileged people. in the same year urban cooperative banks were included in the list of the banks which will provide no frill account services. On 13 December 2005 All the urban commercial banks UCB were directed to publicise NO FRILL ACCOUNT. On 27 December, the role rural regional banks were recognised in achieving the financial inclusion .All the RRBs were advised to provide basic banking no frill account services and Reserve bank of India has also directed RRBs to give wide publicity to the facility of such a no frill account. RRBs were also given directions to provide facility of zero balance account and overdraft facility with complying the guidelines of know your customer account.

General purpose credit facility up to Rs. 25000 was provided to rural and urban population.

2006

In year 2006 the Concept of business facilitators was introduced. On-governmental organisation, self-help group, micro finance institution, civil society organisation were given the role intermediaries in providing financial services at low cost through the use of banking facilitators. Banks were given direction to use club, cooperatives, community, IT enabled rural outlet of corporate entities, post office, insurance agents, panchayat, village knowledge centres, krishi vigyan centre,NGO,micro financial institutions mutually aided corporative etc.RBI has also directed banks to keep a regular check om the working of business correspondence. Banks should ensure that business correspondence should not charge any other fee from the customers.RBI has also directed to constitute grievance redressal machinery for redressing any complaint by business corresopence.RBI has advised all the banks to follow flexible approach on KYC principle. Role of NBFC was recognised as intermediaries in other

words banks were given direction to give the role of business correspondence to non-banking financial institutions.

2007

All the urban commercial banks, state cooperative banks, rural regional banks and urban cooperative banks were advised to take information technology initiative for financial inclusion in the form of smart card, mobile technology to increase the outreach. RBI has launched multi lingual websites in 13 language to fulfil the objective.

2008

On 15 April, RBI has directed that loan should be given not only for consumption and production purpose but also for needs such as shelter improvement and housing facility. In the same month RBI has issued notification that Individuals can be used as business facilitators individuals includes (retired bank employees, ex-serviceman, government employees). Banks branches were also given the responsibility to supervise business correspondence. On 27 August it was notified that Sub agents of business facilitators can be appointed and companies under section 25 can be engaged as business facilitators.

2009-2010

During the year 2009 and 2010, the distance between base branch and business facilitators was increased from 15 km to 30 km. and major findings of working group of financial inclusion was also issued. Banks were also permitted to engage retired bank employees, ex-service man, retired government employees as business correspondence.

2011

On 30 May One district one bank model was introduced through ICT based electronic benefit transfer for routing social security benefits unbanked population having more than 2000 have been allocated to various banks for providing banking services by opening banking outlet by March 2012

On 12 August Guideline for proper allocation of banks to the unbanked village was identified, and all the scheduled commercial banks were asked to open Aadhar enabled bank account for the beneficiaries.

2012

In the year 2012 reserve bank of India has extended the working area of business correspondent. In July reserve bank of India directed regional rural banks to provide the service of Aadhar enabled bank account. In the same year various guidelines have been issued for efficient working of frill account. UCBs were also advised to offer saving bank deposit.

2013

In the month of September reserve bank of India allowed the scheduled commercial banks to distribute banknotes and coins All the scheduled commercial banks have been advised to offer basic saving bank deposit account with certain minimum common facilities to all the customer.

2014

In the year 2014 reserve bank of India formed NACHIKET MOR COMMITTEE for extension of financial services.

VARIOUS COMMITTEES WERE FORMED WITH REGARD TO FINANCIAL INCLUSION-

Rangarajan Committee –The committee was formed by National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) with the objective to enhance the demand for financial services. The Committee recommends that to enhance the financial inclusion supply side and delivery system has to be improved. To improve the demand side efforts should be made for the betterment of human and physical endowments, increasing productivity, mitigating risk and strengthening market linkages regions, segments of the populations and sub-sections of the economy have limited or weak demand for financial services. They also recommended that micro insurance should be linked with micro credit. And continuous initiatives should be taken to contribute maximum to the poor through self-help groups (SHGs) and Microfinance Institutions.

Malegam Committee was formed by reserve bank of India on October 2012 to study issues and concern in the Microfinance Institute. Malegam Committee recommended that a separate category of NBFC has to be created which will specifically work for micro financial sector which will be known as NBFC-MFI. The main objective of this committee is to study the issues and concern related to microfinance

Microfinance Institutions BILL was passed in 2012 instituted by the Finance Department, Government of India. With the sole objective to facilitate access to credit and other financial services to the rural and urban poor and disadvantaged sections of the society. The objective behind this is to achieve financial inclusion of the economy through these institutions.

Nachiket MOR committee (2013)

Nachiket mor committee was formed by reserve bank of India in September 2013 with the objective of providing financial services to small businesses and low income household. This comprehensive committee of financial inclusion aims at providing basic banking and financial services to all the resident through their aadhar card, access points will be set up in the unbanked area, access to credit facility will be provided for that purpose wholesale banks will be set up, investment and insurance facility will be provided at a reasonable cost, financial redresser agency will be set up to protect consumers.

OBJECTIVES

1. To understand the concept and importance of Financial Inclusion.
2. To study the initiatives taken by RBI and Government of India.
3. To analyse the performance of select public sector banks.

ANALYSIS

As per the guidelines of RESERVE BANK OF INDIA and GOVERNMENT OF INDIA the various Banks have set the target for the year 2014, 15 and 16 the authors have made an attempt to analyse the data of select banks namely Bank of Baroda, Central Bank of India and IDBI LTD.

Table 1 shows the data for the year 2014 with respect to total number of rural branches, number of banking outlet in villages with population greater than 2000 and less than 2000, also the data of basic saving bank deposit account have analysed.

FOR THE YEAR 2014					
S.N O.	PARTICULARS	BANK OF BARODA	CENTRAL BANK OF INDIA	ALLAHA BAD BANK	IDBI LTD.
1	Total No. of Branches	4872	4695	2840	1379
2	No. of Rural Branches	1775	1735	1131	246
3	No. of banking outlets in villages with population > 2000	4099	6065	3422	300
4	No. of banking outlets in villages with population < 2000	11206	18376	2500	553
5	Basic Savings Bank Deposit Accounts (BSBDAs) (Bank as a whole)	7731070	14986456	3869375	3108270

Total No. of Branches in the year 2014

No. of Rural Branches in the year 2014

No. of banking outlets in villages with population > 2000 in the year 2014

No. of banking outlets in villages with population < 2000 in the year 2014

During the year 2014, bank of Baroda had 4872 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 1775 which is 36.43% of total branches. On the other central bank of India had targets close enough to bank of Baroda, the total number of branches were 4695, out of which number of rural branches were 1735 which is 36.95% of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with 1735 bank outlets through branch and 4330 through business correspondence. Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence only i.e. those villages had no central banks of India branch. The total number of actual deposit account branches were 8534840 and through BCs were 6451616 making total of 14986456.

Central bank of India had 4695 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 1735 which is of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with bank outlets through branch and through business correspondence and through other modes making total of 6065. Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence 11596 and through other modes 500 which totals 18376.

The total number of actual deposit account branches were 60 lacs and through BCs were 1882000 making total of 14986456.

Allahabad bank had 2840 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 1131 which is of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with bank outlets through branch and through business correspondence and through other modes making total of 3422. Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence and through other modes which totals 2500.

The total number of actual deposit account branches were lacs and through BCs were making total of 3869375.

IDBI BANK LTD had 1379 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 246 which is of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with bank outlets through branch and through business correspondence and through other modes making total of 300. Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence and through other modes which totals 553.

The total number of actual deposit account branches were lacs and through BCs were making total of 3108270.

Table 2 shows the data for the year 2015 with respect to total number of rural branches, number of banking outlet in villages with population greater than 2000 and less than 2000,also the data of basic saving bank deposit account have analysed.

FOR THE YEAR 2015					
S.NO.	PARTICULARS	BANK OF BARODA	CENTRAL BANK OF INDIA	ALLAHABAD BANK	IDBI LTD.
1	Total No. of Branches	5100	5427	3400	1579
2	No. of Rural Branches	1654	2069	1582	332
3	No. of banking outlets in villages with population > 2000	4228	6224	3416	331
4	No. of banking outlets in villages with population < 2000	12096	24768	10963	1000
5	Basic Savings Bank Deposit Accounts (BSBDAs) (Bank as a whole)	7882000	13025812	5500000	3584210

No. of Rural Branches in the year 2015

No. of banking outlets in villages with population > 2000 in the year 2015

During the year 2015, bank of Baroda had 5100 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 1654 which is 32.43% of total branches. On the other hand central bank of India had 5427, out of which number of rural branches were 2069 which is 38.12% of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with 1654 bank outlets through branch and 2534 through business correspondence and through other modes 40 making total of 4228. Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence 11596 and through other modes 500 which totals 12096. The total number of actual deposit account branches were 60 lacs and through BCs were 1882000 making total of 7882000. Central bank of India had 5427 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 2069 which is of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with bank outlets through branch and through business correspondence and through other modes making total of 6224. Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence 11596 and through other modes 500 which totals 24768

The total number of actual deposit account branches were 60 lacs and through BCs were 1882000 making total of 13025812.

Allahabad bank had 5427 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 1582 which is of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with bank outlets through branch and through business correspondence and through other modes making total of 3412 .Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence and through other modes which totals 10963.

The total number of actual deposit account branches were lacs and through BCs were making total of 5500000

IDBI BANK LTD had 5427 branches out of which the number of rural branches were 1582 which is of total branches. The villages with population greater than 2000 were provided with bank outlets through branch and through business correspondence and through other modes making total of 3412 .Whereas in villages with population less than 2000 were provided banking outlet through business correspondence and through other modes which totals 10963.

The total number of actual deposit account branches were lacs and through BCs were making total of 13025812

Conclusion

The present study concludes that though the various norm are being issued from time to time in terms of offering no frill account, opening of zero balance account, flexible approach for KYC norms,kisan credit card ,general credit card, business correspondence, business facilitators, self-help group linkages programme but still banks have not been able to achieve the targets for that these polices has to be reviewed from time to time. It is a well-known facts that the nation's progress can be measured through the effective financial system. In India it is a common fact that while one section of the population has access to the assortment of banking services encompassing regular banking facilities portfolio counselling on the other hand the other segment of underprivileged and lower income group is totally deprived of even basic financial service.so some more efforts has to be taken by RBI AND GOI to provide financial services to the most deprived section of the society

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